

HOUSEHOLD CONSUMPTION PATTERNS IN PAKISTAN: EVIDENCE FROM MICROLEVEL DATA

Shahida Parveen¹, Uzma Nisar²

¹Post-Graduate Student, Department of Economics, The University of Lahore, Sargodha Campus, Pakistan

²Lecturer, Department of Economics, The University of Lahore, Sargodha Campus, Pakistan

ABSTRACT: Consumption is the most significant part of our daily life. How individuals as consumers purchase different things, goods and/or services is called consumption behavior of the households. The study has analyzed the consumption behavior of households in Pakistan using the recent cross-sectional data of HIES 2013-14. The study also checked the validity of Engel's law in case of Pakistan. The results confirm the existence of Engel's law in case of Pakistan.

KEYWORDS: consumption, households, food item, non-food items, durables, utilities

1. INTRODUCTION

Consumption means that a part of income that an individual or group of people spend to meet the basic necessities as well as luxurious standards of life. Furthermore, it may vary to individual to individual or group to group. But the different school of thoughts in economics define it differently. Neo-classicals define it as the final purchases of goods and services by the group of people or individual while other school of thoughts take this concept in a broader sense. Consumption includes the selection of a particular commodity or service, its use as well as recycling of that good or service.

(Mincer, 1963) states that opportunity cost of time has the strong impact on the demand for goods and services as well as home produced substitutes. By the increase of real income, consumption pattern has changed significantly in developing countries especially in a case of Pakistan. It is quite obvious to explore the determinants of varying consumption patterns and to estimate the parameters of the consumption functions for some basket of goods.

(Engel, 1857) seminal work has provided economic planners a framework for analyzing household consumption patterns that is as relevant today as it was 150 years ago. Engel promulgated a realistic law that increase in income leads to decline in the expenditures on food from household's income. The expenditures on food, clothing as well as fuel etc. declines and expenditures on luxurious goods increases with the increase in household's income. Most simply Engle curve states that an increase in households' income, expenditures on basic necessities of life as a proportion of income declines while on the other hand, the proportion of expenditures on luxury goods and services increases (Peter Timmer, Walter Falcon, & Scott Pearson, 1983). Since then a number of studies have been done to check the implication of Engle's Law in a case of both developed and developing countries.

The phenomenon of consumption patterns of households in Pakistan is not new and has been studied by a number of researchers. These studies differed each other in terms of scope, data source and methodology. The findings and recommendations of these studies are also different to each other. Some of the studies used cross-sectional data while others used times series data. Some other studies were also based on interviews from the citizens.

Regardless of the methodology and source of data, the major contribution of these studies was to estimate and test the validity of the association between income and expenditures on commodities. (Burney & Khan, 1991) compared the urban-rural consumption structures in Pakistan. They found the behavioral and structural differences in the consumption patterns of urban and rural households.

This study is of pivotal importance because it is concerned with the household consumption patterns in Pakistan and it also tests the empirical evidence of the Engel's law using cross sectional data in

Corresponding Author Email: shahidaparveenuol@gmail.com

Pakistan.

1.2 Objectives of Study

The main objective of the study is to analyze the consumption behaviour of household in Pakistan using the recent cross-sectional data set of HIES 2013-14. More specifically, the study aims to achieve the following objectives;

1. To estimate the budget share of households and to find out how they are distributing budget share to food, nonfood, durables and utility items.
2. To find out the elasticities of food, non-food, durables and utilities with respect to income.
3. To test the validity of Engel's law in case of Pakistan.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

(Selim, 2001) has pointed out the different variations in consumption behavior of Turkish household using data from the survey of Household Income and Consumption Expenditure 1987-1994. The study has used the double log functional form and estimated the total expenditure elasticities by the weighted least square method. The results show that during this period four consumption commodity groups are statistically significant while five groups have the same trend.

(Gandhimathi, Ambigadevi, & Sundari, 2012) empirically investigated the impact of economic reforms on Indian households. The study covered time period 1970-2005 and it was divided into two parts, pre-reform period 1970-1991 and post-reform period 1991-2005. The study has used secondary data and linear functional form for analyzing. The research showed significant variation in consumption expenditure during both time periods. At the end of the pre-reform period food expenditures were declined from 53.7% to 48.4%. The same trend is also found in a post-reform period and the food expenditure share was declined from 49.9% to 35.4%.

(Ray, 1982) studied demand system by applying the Almost Ideal Demand System (AIDS). The study based on time series and pooled cross-section data from the National budget survey of India. By using non-linear FIML technique for the estimation of data, the results showed that there are significant variations between rural and urban consumer's expenditure. The price and family size have positive effects on the budget share.

(Dudek, 2011) have empirically analyzed the household's food expenditures for Poland. The study used microdata from the three different Household Budget Survey (HBS) for years 2000, 2005 and 2009. Working-Leser model was applied through regression analysis and elasticities were estimated. The results concluded that poor household's consume more on food items and there exist variations in household's behavior towards food expenditures.

(Ahmed, Zaman, & Shah, 2011) tried to find out the effect of remittances on the gross domestic product and also checked the impact of remittances on the welfare of the households. The results of study show that there is positive association between people's spending behavior and remittances and thereby gross domestic product. The major finding of this study is that when inflow of capital assets and remittances increases the households increase expenditures. The study also found that deficit account was covered by the inflow of remittances.

3. METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

3.1 Conceptual Framework and Econometric Models

A consumer maximizes his/her utility subject to his/her budget constraint. The constrained utility maximization function may be written as follows:

$$(1) \quad \text{Max}U = U(x) \text{ Subject to } \sum_{i=0}^n p_i x_i \leq M$$

Where utility is the function of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i which are quantities of i^{th} goods. Total expenditures on goods and services are equal to or less than total income or budget M . There are many functional form for estimating the Engle's law. In this study, to examine the household consumption behavior and patterns, we have followed the famous Working-Leser function (Leser, 1963; Working, 1943) which relates linear budget shares to the logarithm of household's total expenditure.

3.2 Model Selection Criteria for Engel Aggregation

The selection of functional form of the model for the expenditure shares depends on the level of importance given to a variety of properties that are desired by the function to possess. The functional form of the model in this paper is mainly intended to follow certain criteria: (i) the curve should be appropriate in case of a variety of goods; (ii) it must support precisely for increasing, constant and decreasing marginal propensities in spending on an array of expenditure levels; and (iii) it must be coherent with the additive criteria i.e., the summation of marginal propensities for all the goods must be equivalent to unity (Adams Jr, 2006). Taking all these considerations into account, the adjusted Working-Leser curve has been used as it was used by (Bhalotra & Attfield, 1998; Deaton & Case, 2002). The model is specified of the form:

$$(2) \quad \delta_{ij} = a_j + b_i \ln C_i + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

where

$$\delta_{ij} = \frac{c_j}{\exp_i}$$

and

$i=1,2,\dots,n$.

$j=1,2,\dots,k$.

Where δ_{ij} is the expenditure share spent on j^{th} good by the i^{th} household and $\ln C_i$ is the natural log of household total expenditures. ε_{ij} is the residual term. Modifying the Working-Leser function, the present study has included a number of other variables in the model. In addition, we have also analyzed the relationship between consumption and budget shares of households which is called the Engel's law. It describes the relationship between food expenditures and the total expenditures of a household. Specifically we have used the following empirical models for estimating four consumption categories of households. How much expenditure share is devoted to food consumption by households is evaluated using equation (3)

$$(3) \quad \delta_f = b_1 + b_2 \ln C_i + b_3 HhSize + b_4 DRemit + b_5 AgeDep \\ + b_6 HHgender + b_7 region + b_8 DmotherEdu + \varepsilon_i$$

To estimate the relationship between non-food expenditure and total consumption expenditures the study has used equation (4)

$$(4) \quad \delta_{nf} = b_1 + b_2 \ln C_i + b_3 HhSize + b_4 DRemit + b_5 AgeDep \\ + b_6 HHgender + b_7 region + b_8 DmotherEdu + \varepsilon_i$$

The relationship of expenditure on durable good and expenditure on utilities with the total expenditures has been estimated with the help of equation (5) and equation (6).

$$(5) \quad \delta_d = b_1 + b_2 \ln C_i + b_3 HhSize + b_4 DRemit + b_5 AgeDep \\ + b_6 HHgender + b_7 region + b_8 DmotherEdu + \varepsilon_i$$

$$(6) \quad \delta_u = b_1 + b_2 \ln C_i + b_3 HhSize + b_4 DRemit + b_5 AgeDep + b_6 HHgender + b_7 region + b_8 DmotherEdu + \varepsilon_i$$

Where δ_f , δ_{nf} , δ_d and δ_u are ratios of household food, nonfood, durables and utilities expenditures to total expenditures. At the end we have evaluated the expenditure elasticities for these four consumption classes, such as food, nonfood, durables and utilities by using the expenditure elasticities formula, which is $e_i = 1 + \frac{b_i}{\delta_i}$.

(Browne & Hendriks, 2007; Davis et al., 2007; Dudek, 1954; Stigler, 1954) have used same approach for measuring expenditure elasticities. Expenditures elasticities are defined as percentage change in demand of goods due to percentage change in expenditure.

3.3 Description of Variables

Recent study has used four dependent variables including six independent variables. To build the structural and behavioral differences in spending behavior dummy variables are also used. Ordinary Least Square regression technique has been used to estimate the models. All dependent and independent variables are illustrated in table 1 and table 2.

Table 1 Description of dependent variables

Dependent variables	Illustrations
Income share of Food Expenditure (δ_f)	The Ratio of food expenditure and total expenditure $\left(\delta_f = \frac{f \text{ exp}}{t \text{ exp}} \right)$
Income share of Non-food Expenditure (δ_{nf})	The Ratio of non-food expenditure and total expenditure $\left(\delta_{nf} = \frac{n - food \text{ exp}}{t \text{ exp}} \right)$
Income share of Durable Goods (δ_d)	The Ratio of durables expenditure and total expenditure $\left(\delta_d = \frac{durables \text{ exp}}{t \text{ exp}} \right)$
Income share of Utilities (δ_u)	The Ratio of utilities expenditure and total expenditure $\left(\delta_u = \frac{utility \text{ exp}}{t \text{ exp}} \right)$

Table 2 Description of independent variables

Independent Variables	Illustrations
Household size	No. of persons
Remittances(dummy)	If remittances receive=1 and not receive=0
Dependency ratio	Household size / number of earning members
Household head Gender (dummy)	If male= 1 and female=0
Region(dummy)	If urban=1 and rural=0
Mother's Education (dummy)	If literate=1 and illiterate=0

Table 3 Number of observations in the data

Region	Total	Percentage
Rural	11755	65.35
Urban	6234	34.65
	17989	100%

Source: (HIES, 2014)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Regression analysis results are provided in this section. The results in table 4 showed that there exists negative relationship between food expenditures share and log of total expenditures which simply demonstrates that if total expenditures increase, the spending on food items decreases. Calculated results of current study figure out that 1 percent increase in total expenditures causes to decrease the ratio of budget share of food items by 0.001054 units.. The findings are consistent with the studies by (Siddiqui, 1982) and (Burney & Khan, 1991). The reason can be due to the fact that as one's expenditures increases, the ratio of food expenditures in total should decrease as the food consumption cannot go beyond a specific limit.

Table 4 OLS Estimation of Budget Share for Food Items

Variables	Coefficients	Standard Error	t-value	P-value
Log of Total Expenditure	-0.1054	0.00187	-56.36	0.000
Household Size	0.0098	0.00033	29.70	0.000
Remittances(1=received,0=not received)	-0.0037	0.00217	-1.71	0.082
Dependency ratio	0.0179	0.00358	5.00	0.000
HH Gender(1 male,0 female)	0.0323	0.00462	6.99	0.000
Region(1 urban,0 rural)	-0.0557	0.00176	-31.65	0.000
Mother Education	-0.0025	0.0002	-12.50	0.000
Constant	1.454	0.01809	80.38	0.000
R²	0.364	F-Stat (Prob.)	1711.52 (0.000)	

Source: Author's Own Calculations

In case of household size budget share of food also represents direct relationship. The coefficient of household size is significant and positive which means that there is direct relationship between size of the household and share of food expenditure. The coefficient of household size is 0.0098 means an increase of one member in the household causes increase the ratio of food budget by 0.0098 units. On the other hand, the coefficient of remittances dummy is negative which shows that the household who receive remittances spend less amount on food as compared to households who do not receive remittances. It further explains that the remittances received by the household are spent more on luxuries of life as compared to food items or necessities of life.

The positive coefficient of dependency ratio shows that the budget share of food items increase with the increase in dependency ratio at household level.

The coefficient of dependency ratio shows that with a unit increase in dependency ratio the share of

food expenditure of the household will increase by 0.0179 units. Households' with higher dependency ratio are more likely to spend more on food items than those households having lower level of dependency ratio. The results are consistent with the study by (Hassan & Chandra Babu, 1980).

Estimated result of gender of household head dummy (with 1 for male and 0 for female) also has positive effect on budget share of food item which represents that households with male heads spend more on food items as compared to female-headed households. Similarly calculated results of regional dummy (with 1 for urban and 0 for rural) has negative relationship with budget share of food items. This represents that households from urban areas devote less share of total expenditure for food as compared to household from rural areas.

The coefficient mother education is -0.0025 which means that one extra year of mother education will decrease the share of food expenditure in total budget by 0.0025 units. Hence mother education negatively affect share of food expenditures of the households.

Like regression estimates current study has also estimated the elasticity of budget share of food items.

Estimated measure of elasticity is $e_i = 1 + \frac{b_i}{\delta_i} = \left[1 + \frac{-0.1054}{0.4688} = 0.78 \right]$ which is less than one and shows

that food item are less elastic. It also represents that these items are necessities of life and households spend on food items without regarding the amount of their income however quality of food changes with the difference in income.

Table 5 OLS Estimation of Budget Share for Non- Food Items

Variables	Coefficients	Standard Error	t-value	P-value
Log of Total Expenditure	0.0065	0.00147	4.41	0.000
Household Size	-0.001	0.00022	-4.48	0.000
Remittances(1 received, 0 not received)	-0.0061	0.00158	-3.86	0.000
Dependency ratio	-0.009	0.00254	-3.55	0.000
HH Gender(1 male, 0 female)	0.0121	0.00332	3.65	0.000
Region(1 urban, 0 rural)	-0.0086	0.00128	-6.73	0.000
Mother Education	0.0005	0.00015	3.26	0.001
Constant	0.1788	0.01414	12.64	0.000
R²	0.0077	F-Stat (Prob.)	17.38 (0.000)	

Source: Author's Own Calculations

The results in table 5 show that budget share of non-food items has positive relationship with log of total expenditure. It shows that increase in total expenditures comes with the increase in budget share of non-food items. The positive relation shows that when the total expenditures of the household will increase they will spend more of their resources on non-food items. The results are supporting the findings of (Davis et al., 2007).

Similarly estimates of household size represent that if household size increases, the budget share of non-food items will decrease. The comparison of results for non-food and food items clearly shows that the rise in household size increases the budget share for necessities of life as compared to luxuries of life. Estimated results of remittances show that if remittances increase budget share of non-food items

decrease. The coefficient of dependency ratio demonstrates that if number of dependents increases in a house the budget share of non-food items will decrease. The coefficient of household-head gender dummy, which is 1 for male and 0 for female, is positive which simply shows that male headed households spend more budget share on non-food items as compared to female headed households. Coefficient of regional dummy represents that households belong to rural areas spends more on non-food items as compared to urban areas. The coefficient of mother education shows a positive relation with budget share of non-food items.

Estimated elasticity of non-food item is $e_i = 1 + \frac{b_i}{\delta_i} = \left[1 + \frac{0.0065}{0.2382} = 1.03 \right]$ which is greater than unity

and designate that non-food items are elastic. Estimated elasticity shows that households increase spending on non-food items when they face increase in income.

Table 6 OLS Estimation of Budget Share for Durables Items

Variables	Coefficients	Standard Error	t-value	P-value
Log of Total Expenditure	0.0748	0.00230	32.50	0.000
Household Size	-0.0070	0.00033	-21.14	0.000
Remittances(1 received, 0 not received)	0.0076	0.00210	3.64	0.000
Dependency ratio	-0.0041	0.00342	-1.20	0.228
HH Gender(1 male, 0 female)	-0.0393	0.00469	-8.37	0.000
Region(1 urban, 0 rural)	0.0696	0.00181	38.50	0.000
Mother Education	0.0025	0.00022	11.43	0.000
Constant	-0.4275	0.02176	-19.65	0.000
R²	0.328	F-Stat (Prob.)	1049.29 (0.000)	

Source: Author’s Own Calculations

The results of regression model for budget share of durables items are shown in table 6. The results show that total expenditures and budget share of durables items have positive relationship. One percent increase in total expenditures increases the ratio of budget share of durables by 0.000748 units. The increase in household size decreases the budget share of durables items. The coefficient of remittances shows positive relationship with expenditures share of durables items which implies that households receiving remittances spend more on durables goods as compared to those who are not receiving such remittances. The result of dependency ratio is negative but are insignificant which means the increase in dependency ratio has no effect on budget share of durable goods. The male-headed households spend lower share of budget on durable goods as compared to female-headed households. Similarly regional dummy is positive and shows that the budget share of durables items among urban households is higher than the rural households. Mother education has also positive effect on budget share of durables items that means expenditure on durables items increases with the increase in the years of mother education.

Estimated elasticity of durable item is $e_i = 1 + \frac{b_i}{\delta_i} = \left[1 + \frac{0.0748}{0.2759} = 1.27 \right]$ which clearly greater than

unity and designate that durable items are elastic. Estimated elasticity shows that households spend more on durable items when they face increase in income and spend less on durable items when there income decreases.

Table 7 OLS Estimation of Budget Share for Utilities

Variables	Coefficients	Standard Error	t-value	P-value
Log of Total Expenditure	0.02368	0.00175	13.53	0.000
Household Size	-0.00173	0.00019	-8.83	0.000
Remittances(1 received, 0 not received)	0.002157	0.00082	2.61	0.009
Dependency ratio	-0.00440	0.00146	-3.02	0.002
HH Gender(1 male, 0 female)	-0.00539	0.00176	-3.06	0.000
Region(1 urban, 0 rural)	-0.00510	0.00084	-6.01	0.000
Mother Education	-0.000437	0.00011	-3.94	0.000
Constant	-0.20185	0.01620	-12.46	0.000
R²	0.070	F-Stat (Prob.)	41.06 (0.000)	

Source: Author's Own Calculations

The results in table 7 show that total expenditures has positive impact on budget share of utilities that's simply means that one percent increase in expenditures leads to 0.002368 units increase in the ratio of budget share of utilities. Household's size show a negative relationship with budget share of utilities. The coefficient of remittances dummy is positive. The households who receive remittances spend more share of budget on utilities as compared to those households who do not receive remittances. The dependency ratio displays an inverse relation with budget share of utilities. The rise in dependency ratio decline the budget share devoted for utilities. The coefficient of gender dummy (1 for male 0 for female) reveals that male headed household has less spending on utilities as compared to female headed households. The coefficient of region dummy shows that household in urban areas spend less budget share on utilities as compared to households from rural areas. Mother education is also negatively associated with budget share of utilities.

Estimated elasticity of utilities item is $e_i = 1 + \frac{b_i}{\delta_i} = \left[1 + \frac{0.02368}{0.0171} = 2.38 \right]$ which clearly greater than

unity and designate that utilities items are elastic. Estimated results of elasticity show that households increase spending on utilities items when they face increase in income.

5. CONCLUSION

This study has attempted to check the existence of Engle Curve in the case of Pakistan. Therefore, HIES dataset for the year of 2013-14 has been used. Four different regression models are brought under analysis. These regression models are used to check the impact of log of total expenditure, household size, remittances, dependency ratio, gender, region, and mother education on food items, non-food items, durables, and utilities.

The regression analysis for food items reveals that all independent variables including log of total expenditure, household size, dependency ratio, gender, region, and mother education, have significant impact on the food items expect remittances. The regression analysis for non-food items shows that all

independent variables including log of total expenditure, household size, remittances, dependency ratio, gender, region, and mother education have significant impact on non-food items. It is found that log of total expenditure, household size, remittances, gender, region, and mother education have significant impact on the durables items except the dependency ratio. The analysis of utilities shows that all the independent variables including log of total expenditure, household size, remittances, Age dependency ratio, gender, region, and mother education, have significant impact on the utilities.

It is recommended that the prices of food items should be controlled by the government as the demand for food items is inelastic and people will be bound to purchase these items even at the high prices.

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